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Research Article

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL ANTI-DANDRUFF SHAMPOO BY USING ALBIZIA AMARA AND CYNODON DACTYLON POWDER**Vasanthan.A¹, Senthil Kumar K. L², Gokulan P. D³, S. Anjali⁴, A. Jeevadharsini⁴, K. Prabha⁴.**¹Associate professor, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.²Principal, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.³Professor, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.⁴B. Pharm students, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.**Abstract:**

The Yeast like Malassezia furfur fungal infection leads to dandruff formation. Dandruff cannot be fully eliminated but can be effectively controlled. The aim of the present study is to formulate and evaluate the herbal Anti dandruff shampoo. The prepared formulation not only cleans the dirt and dandruff but also makes controls hair fall promotes hair growth, keeps cool head and shiny hair. The formulation uses herbs like Albizia Amara and Cynodon dactylon leaves powder extracts and other ingredients for preparing base shampoo which make an effective anti-dandruff formulation with healthy scalp. The formulated shampoo was subjected to evaluation parameters like physical appearance, pH, surface tension, viscosity, dirt dispersion, wetting time, foaming ability, skin irritation test, percentage solid content test, stability test, etc. The main goal of the present study is to formulate and evaluate anti-dandruff shampoo for treating various hair and scalp problem. The results showed that the herbal shampoo formulation exhibited good physicochemical properties and significant antimicrobial activity against Malassezia furfur. The study suggests that the herbal anti-dandruff shampoo formulation using Albizia Amara and Cynodon dactylon has potential as a natural remedy for the treatment of dandruff.

Key words: Albizia Amara, Cynodon dactylon, Herbal shampoo, Dandruff control, cleansing action.

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INTRODUCTION:

Plants are made up of many elements that perform a variety of biological functions required for disease resistance or therapy. Dandruff is a skin ailment caused by the *Malassezia* fungus, which affect the scalp, making it itchy and greasy⁽¹⁾. Dandruff is a prevalent scalp disease that affects about 50% of the population. Keratinocytes have a critical role in the expression and development of immune reactions during dandruff formation⁽²⁾. Dandruff becomes more severe during the winter months. To treat dandruff, various shampoos were utilized, including synthetic and beneficial preparations.

Herbal shampoo is a form of cosmetic preparation that contains herbs, which are natural plant ingredients⁽³⁾. An 'herbal shampoo' is any hair cleaning solution that contains extracts of Ayurvedic herbs and flowers. The shampoo has numerous functions, including lubrication, conditioning, hair growth, decrease of hair loss, maintenance of hair color, and medication⁽⁴⁾. It also serves important functions such as anti-dandruff, cleaning, and keratolytic. The primary goal of shampoo preparation is to remove impurities and dandruff while also leaving hair soft and silky⁽⁵⁾.

The current study's goal is to avoid using commercially accessible synthetic or chemical preparations. Several herbal substances with antidandruff characteristics were employed, resulting in silky, lustrous hair that promotes hair development⁽⁶⁾. Importantly, these preparations are rather inexpensive. The plants used for the formulation such as *Albizia Amara* and *Cynodon dactylon*.

DANDRUFF

Dandruff is a scalp disease caused by flaking of the scalp's skin tissues, resulting in white flakes that occur all over the scalp and hair shafts. It's a frequent difficulty that everyone faces at some point in their lives. It is because flaking is a natural process of removing dead skin cells off the scalp, and while dandruff's natural existence cannot be totally eliminated, excessive and chronic levels of dandruff require care, making anti-dandruff treatment of primary importance.

CLASSIFICATION OF DANDRUFF:

Depending upon the symptoms dandruff categorize

- 1) Dry dandruff
- 2) Oily dandruff

DRY DANDRUFF:

Dry (common) dandruff, also known as Pityriasis simplex, is characterized by the excessive development of minute white, grayish, or ashen scales that accumulate on the scalp. A flaking scalp indicates a high level of dandruff, and it is time to consider anti-

dandruff treatment. The first indicators may be a simple dry scalp, which can worsen owing to eczema or psoriasis.

OIL DANDRUFF:

Oil dandruff is sometimes called pityriasis steatoides. It appears on the scalp skin, with varying levels of sebum production. It is more common in young males after puberty (ages 18–24). Inflammation of varying intensity develops on the scalp skin, as do oily scales of dirty yellow colour, which can form lesions.

SYMPTOMS OF DANDRUFF

- ❖ Hair loss due to excessive scratching.
- ❖ Flaking skin on the scalp.
- ❖ Redness and inflammation of the scalp.
- ❖ Dryness and tightness of the scalp

SHAMPOO

Shampoo is a hair care product that comes in the form of a viscous liquid and is used to cleanse the hair. Shampoo having a surfactant (i.e., surface active substance) in an appropriate form (liquids, solids, or powder) that, when used as directed, removes surface grease, grime, and skin debris from the hair shaft and scalp without harming the user. Most shampoos contain water, a detergent (cleaning agent), a surfactant (lather-making agent), scent (natural and synthetic), preservatives, and coloring. With the exception of water and salt (sodium chloride), different chemical compounds are utilized depending on the desired outcome of the shampoo.

IDEAL PROPERTIES OF SHAMPOO

- ✓ To make the hair smooth and shiny.
- ✓ Produce good amount of foam.
- ✓ It should not cause irritation scalp, skin and eye.
- ✓ It should be completely, effectively remove dirt.
- ✓ Impart pleasant fragrance to hair.
- ✓ It should be easily and completely removed on rinsing with water.

HERBAL SHAMPOO

Herbal shampoo is a hair care product made from natural materials such as plants, herbs, and botanical extracts. Unlike regular shampoos, which may contain synthetic chemicals, herbal shampoos rely on the medicinal characteristics of different plants to wash and nourish the hair and scalp. They can also promote hair development, treat hair loss, and restore damaged hair. Herbal shampoos can help relieve itchy scalps.

BENEFITS OF HERBAL SHAMPOO

- Fights dandruff
- Free from side effects
- Promote hair growth
- Nourishes the roots
- Prevents scalp itchiness

METHODOLOGY:**INGREDIENTS**

- Albizia amara
- Cyanodon dactylon
- Sodium lauryl sulfate
- Hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose
- Glycerin
- Citric acid
- Methyl paraben
- Lavender oil

ALBIZIA AMARA:

SYNONYMS: Silk tree, Usila tree

AYURVEDIC NAME: Arappu

KINGDOM: Plantae

FAMILY: Fabaceae

USES:

- ✓ Reduce scalp irritation and inflammation.
- ✓ Helps remove dead skin cells, reducing dandruff and flakiness.

ALBIZIA AMARA POWDER**CYNODON DACTYLON:**

SYNONYMS: Bermuda grass

AYURVEDIC NAME: Arugampul

KINGDOM: Plantae

FAMILY: Poaceae

USES:

- ✓ Anti-inflammatory properties.
- ✓ Improve blood circulation in the scalp.

CYNODON DACTYLON POWDER

FORMULATION OF HERBAL SHAMPOO

Methods of preparation:

The herbal anti-dandruff shampoo was prepared by simple mixing process. The ingredients used in the shampoo are SLS as surfactants, HPMC is used as thickening agent, Albizia amara and Bermuda grass leaves powder extracts are used as anti-dandruff agent, citric acid as pH adjuster, methylparaben as preservatives and lavender oil used as a perfume. The extracts of all herbals were mixed with other ingredients as enlisted in the table 1. The final herbal Antidandruff formulations were stored in suitable plastic containers and used for further evaluation parameters.

Table: 1 composition of herbal shampoo

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3
1	Albizia amara extract	2ml	2ml	2ml
2	Cynodon dactylon extract	2ml	2ml	2ml
3	Sodium lauryl sulphate	15gm	12gm	10gm
4	HPMC	1 gm	0.4gm	1.5gm
5	Citric acid	1ml	1ml	1ml
6	Methyl paraben	0.7gm	0.1 gm	0.3gm
7	Glycerin	0.5ml	1ml	0.3ml
8	Lavender oil	1ml	1ml	1ml
9	Purified water	q.s	q.s	q.s

EVALUATION OF HERBAL SHAMPOO

1. Physical appearance:

The formulation prepared was evaluated for the clarity, colour, odour and foam producing ability.

2. Determination of pH:

Developed formulation was diluted using distilled water to prepare a sample with 10 % concentration. The prepared sample was checked for pH using a digital pH meter at room temperature $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

3. Foaming ability:

Cylinder shake method with slight modification was used for determining foaming ability. 50ml of the 1% shampoo solution was put into a 250 ml graduated measuring cylinder and covered with hand. Measuring cylinder was shaken for 1 minute. The total volume of the foam contents after 1 minute shaking was recorded. The procedure was continued for 5 minutes.

4. Determination of percentage solids contents:

A clean dry china dish was weighed and added with 4 grams of shampoo. The dish with shampoo was weighed. The exact weight of the shampoo was calculated. The china dish with shampoo was placed on the hot plate until the liquid portion was evaporated. The weight after drying was calculated.

5. Dirt dispersion:

Two drops of shampoo were added in a large test tube contain 10 ml of distilled water. 1 drop of India ink was added; the test tube was stoppered and shakes it ten times. The amount of ink in the foam was estimated as None, Light, Moderate, or Heavy.

6. Surface tension measurement:

Dilute the shampoo using distilled water to fix 10% as concentration. Measurements were carried out using stalagmometer. (7)

7. Skin irritation test:

Prepared herbal shampoo was applied on skin for 5 minutes after that was washed and tested for irritation or inflammation to the skin.

8. Antimicrobial Activity:

In this method the agar is melted, cooled at 45°C , inoculate with the test microorganism and then pour in the sterile petri plate. In this method when the agar plate has been solidified then holes about 9mm in diameter in the medium with sterile cork borer, Then the antimicrobial agent is placed in the hole and in another hole placed marketed formulation acts as standard, the diameter of zone of inhibition were measured after inoculation at $30-35^\circ\text{C}$ for 2-3 days. The diameter of zone of inhibition gives an indication of the relative activity of different antimicrobial substance against tested microorganism.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Results for all the three herbal anti-dandruff formulations F1, F2, F3 are shown in table 2. The color of all the three formulations is light brown Colour, viscous in nature, smooth and good foam. The pH of all the three formulations F1, F2, F3 was 5.4, 5.17, 4.59 respectively, which was non-irritation to the skin according to the skin irritation test. The dirt dispersion test is also high in for all the three formulations. The surface tension test of all three formulations was 30.42, 34.01, and 31.10 within the limit. The percentage solid content in all the three formulations are 22.52, 20.56, and 25.13. The antimicrobial test for F3 formulation is good as compared to F1 and F2 formulations.

Table2: Evaluation parameters of herbal shampoo

S.No	Evaluation parameters	Observation
1	Appearance	Light brown
2	Ph	4 - 5.5
3	Dirt dispersion test	Light
4	% solid content test	20.56 - 25.13
5	Skin irritation test	Non-irritation
6	Surface tension test	30.42 - 34.01

CONCLUSION:

The main aim of the formulated herbal anti-dandruff shampoo was to prevent dandruff and various hair problems. Evaluation studies showed good appearance, good wash ability, non-irritant to the skin, good foam stability, good dirt dispersion activity. pH of the formulated herbal antidandruff shampoos is near to the neutral, shows that the formulations are non-irritant to the skin. The evaluation study on our shampoo contains good characters of an ideal shampoo and found to be harmless and cost effective.

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